

Upcycling of Construction Materials and Products

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ABSTRACT

Urbanization and population growth are driving an increase in construction activities, leading to a rise in construction and demolition waste (CDW). The construction industry is responsible for 9 Gtpa of global waste, generated at various stages in the building lifecycle. To reduce environmental impacts, the industry must move away from a wasteful linear way of working and adopt a circular economy, where materials never become waste. The circular economy involves directly reusing or recycling materials and components. However, the market for construction materials and products is challenged by insufficient information, poor perception of secondary materials, and inconsistent information on quality. The availability of traceable data can improve end-user confidence, increase public acceptance of secondary materials, and promote circularity. This paper identifies the data required to improve reusability and upcycling of construction materials and products at end-of-life. Starting with an awareness of the problem through a literature review of articles, documents, technical reports, and government guidelines, existing research gaps around this matter are identified, and a synthesis of required data at the end of the life of products is presented. With this information, it is developed an initial proposal of a framework for decision-making processes at the end-of-service life for buildings and infrastructures to be applied in pre-demolition audits. This forms part of a bigger study that adopts the design science methodology, covering this way the first two stages. This paper's outcome will help identify the data required in conducting end-of-life assessments for buildings, using pre-demolition audits, which will be useful in describing the reusability and recyclability aspects of construction assets. This could ultimately enable data-driven applications to support more accurate decision-making procedures for waste recovery in different scenarios in the construction industry.

Keywords: pre-demolition audit; upcycling; construction materials; construction product; design science.

INTRODUCTION

According to Li et al. (2022) the construction industry will continue to dominate the raw materials consumption among other sectors until 2060. The problem with the construction industry is that a considerable quantity of waste is generated across the stages from design to construction, and operations, but the highest waste volumes come from demolition at the end of service life, which has now become a burden environmentally, economically, and socially (Ginga et., 2020; Osmani, 2011). Activities in the construction industry are accountable for producing 9 Gtpa of waste globally and account for a third of the total waste that is generated in EU countries. According to the data from the European Union (EU) (2023), over 807million tonnes of construction and demolition waste (CDW) was produced among the 27 countries in Europe in 2020 and there is a projected growth from \$108.74 billion in 2021 to \$142.92 billion by 2028 in the global construction and demolition market at compounded annual growth rate (CAGR) of 4.0% (GOV.UK, 2021).

Byers et al., (2024) state that reused products and components are only about 1% from deconstruction. Comprehensive material inventories are useful in accounting for the estimated waste from the demolition of the building, pre-demolition audit is a practical tool to conduct material inventory. Ehlert et al. (2019) assert that pre-demolition audits are essential for resource management and controlled demolition but beyond this is the need to account for the material and promote recovery for the material with useful life inside. Following the design science strategy, this paper aims to cover two differentiated stages:

- a) Stage 1. Identification of data sets required in the applications of pre-demolition audits for adequate decision-making on waste management and recovery.
- b) Stage 2. Development of a framework proposal for decision-making processes at the end-of-service life for buildings and infrastructures to be applied in pre-demolition audits.

MATERIAL METHOD

Design Science Research (DSR), as proposed by Simon, (1996), is a pragmatic research approach that encourages the creation of innovative solutions to real-world issues. Geerts, (2011) states that Design science is a common methodology in engineering and architecture and is focused on creating an artifact (Artifact, 2010) which could be concepts, models, methods, or instantiations (March and Smith, 1995). DSR is aimed at solving an unresolved problem in a unique way that is more efficient and effective (Hevner et. al., (2004). Johannesson and Perjons (2021) affirm that many practical problems can be solved using artifacts. An 'artifact' is illustrated as an artificial object developed by people to solve practical difficulties (Johannesson & Perjons, 2012). The

artifacts can be actual objects or diagrams, a set of instructions, or an information and communication technology solution. Following this principle, a framework for decision-making processes at the end of service life for buildings and infrastructure can be termed an artifact in DSR. Therefore, a step-by-step process is defined to develop an initial flow map for pre-demolition audits, and the results from the first two stages are presented in this paper. Design science methodology allows the development of a predictive model for practical application to the research problem. It defines a cyclic development and assessment process that first outlines a problem in the construction industry, then proposes that a new method or expertise can solve that problem, and finally evaluates whether the new solution is effective for the intended users and in the proposed environment (Adegoke & Ang, 2019; Baskerville et al., 2018; Kehily & Underwood, 2017). The DSR process is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Design Science Process (Baskerville et al., 2018; Kehily & Underwood, 2017).

The project is divided into five phases according to the design science strategy, which are the following:

Phase 1 – Awareness of the problem: the research method for this phase is made following a literature review which is used to produce the research gaps and identify the problem. Vaishnavi and Kuechler (2008) affirm that multiple sources are required to create an awareness of the problem. This was done through a literature review of articles, documents, technical reports, and government guidelines, existing research gaps around this matter are identified, and a synthesis of required data at the end of the service life of products is presented.

Phase 2 – Suggestion: the suggestion is a proposal drawn from the findings in the literature review. The proposal that is created from the literature review includes diagrams and a flow map for a

pre-demolition audit developed to address the research problem for construction materials and products at the end of service life for buildings.

This paper covers part of the work developed in phases one and two of design science research, presenting a summary of data required at the end of life for final destiny evaluation obtained from the literature review, and the framework proposal for the pre-demolition audit process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed framework for decision-making processes at the end-of-service life for buildings and infrastructures to be applied in pre-demolition audits is presented in Figure 3. The proposed framework takes into consideration the roles of each stakeholder and their interactions with material data in the demolition process and how this can support a pre-demolition audit. The details of the symbols are shown in Figure 2:

	Start and end of a flowchart
	Processing of data or calculations
	Decision
	Input or output of data
	A document or report
	A subroutine
	A flow of logic

Figure 2. Flowchart symbols and meaning.

The proposed pre-demolition flow map was drawn from the results derived from the literature review of articles, documents, legislation, and technical reports on the pre-demolition audit. The initial flow map was presented in consultation meetings with project partners. Further inputs were taken to improve the proposal and subjected to more scrutiny using different scenarios that could play out with the changes in the construction industry such as lack of building documentation or incomplete information. The European Union Construction & Demolition Waste Management Protocol including guidelines for pre-demolition and pre-renovation audits of buildings was a critical guide followed in development. Some of the regulations consulted are the Building Safety Regulation, Site Waste Management Plan Regulations 2008, control of Substances Hazardous to Health, control of Asbestos Regulation 2012, The Construction (Design and Management) Regulations (CDM) 2015, Waste (England and Wales) Regulations 2011, Hazardous Waste Regulations 2005, and Waste Management Hierarchy Directive 2008/98/EC.

Figure 3. Propose pre-demolition flow map. Source: Author's own

The circles on the left side of the flow map represent the stakeholders and the stage at which their input is required, the first stakeholder is the property owner while the waste facility manager will be the last on the chain of command but a strong collaboration is required among all the stakeholders for a successful implementation of the flow map to achieve the desire upcycling of materials and products at end-of-life of building. The phases of the waste audit are covered in the flow map, the desk study starts immediately after the property owner indicates interest in demolishing the building by providing the waste auditor with the necessary document that will be

used to apply for a demolition permit from the Government and preliminary report on the property. After the desk study, a field study is mandatory to complement the findings from the desk study to account for the changes that were not recorded on the building document and the changes in the building environment which will not be covered by any existing document. The surroundings will have changed from other developmental plans that need to be considered when developing the site waste management plan and deciding on the demolition method. The waste auditor will generate the inventory of materials during the site visit and desk study which will identify all the materials and products and special attention to the hazardous materials that will require specialist removal. A recommendation on the suitable demolition process should be made in the report and the best upcycling option for materials and products following the waste hierarchy created by the European Union guidelines on demolition with a focus on direct reuse or preparing for reuse before recovery and other options. Recommendation for testing may be required if an accurate decision cannot be made after visual inspection during the site visit, samples will be taken for non-destructive testing or as may be required. Treatment suggestions for recovered materials and quality certification for secondary materials and products will be part of the report that will be submitted to the management as the outcome of the pre-demolition audits.

CONCLUSION

This study provides the findings from the literature review on pre-demolition audits and through design science methodology developed a framework that will digitalise the process for conducting a pre-demolition audit toward the reuse of construction materials and products which is based on the deliberations made throughout the research analysis. This research aims to make both real-world and scholarly contributions by discovering problems with the upcycling of construction materials and products at the end of service life which is accountable for the largest volume of waste by identifying the datasets required in the application of pre-demolition audits for decision-making in waste recovery. The recovery rate for CDW might be high but are mostly for low-value purposes which is downcycling. Pre-demolition audits are presented as solutions to downcycling and challenges facing materials and products at the end-of-service life. Moreso, pre-demolition audits will increase user's confidence in secondary materials and be a fundamental part of building construction, deconstruction, and reconstruction projects. This study proposes a framework for decision-making processes at the end-of-service life for buildings and infrastructures to be applied in pre-demolition audits. The framework proposes a novel and more efficient method for the pre-demolition audit and reuse process for buildings at

end-of-service life in a built environment, specifically an information-driven approach.

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